

INSECURITY AND NIGERIA’S FOREIGN POLICY

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Abstract: *In the last decades, insecurity has emerged as one of the major challenges facing Nigeria. This has resulted in heavy loss of lives, destruction of properties both state own and private as well as the displacements of citizens in the affected areas which have negatively affected the image of the country on the global stage. It is without doubt that increase in the spate of various forms of insecurity, including kidnapping, banditry, terrorism, and insurgency, has practically put the lives of the citizens at a huge risk and undermined the economic, political, and social stability of the country. It is in line with the above that this study is poised to identify and contribute to one of the most challenging issues in the country - insecurity from the lens of the perceptions of the country’s foreign policy at the world stage; how it affects the country’s foreign relations and domestic socio-economic and political realities and also proffer solutions to remedying it. This study adopts the Linkage Politics framework of analysis relying on data collected through secondary sources from the existing literature, journals, government official documents, newspapers, and web-based materials among others to assess how insecurity has impacted the country’s foreign policy. Findings revealed that issues relating to poor governance, corruption, unemployment, ethnic-religious conflicts, and poverty are the contributors to insecurity in Nigeria. Furthermore, the international media coverage of the country’s security crises has helped fuel the perception of Nigeria as a restive zone or a high-risk environment. As the Federal Government strives to solve the insecurity crisis and its attendant consequences, the seeming inability to fully tackle the root causes of insecurity has perpetuated a situation of revolving violence and instability in Nigeria. The study, conclude that the Federal Government must stand up to its primary responsibility of securing the lives and properties of its citizens, tackle the root causes of insecurity through a wholistic socio-economic and political reforms. It recommends a re-jig of the machinery of Nigeria’s foreign policy as well as an engagement in international image laundering of the country.*

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Introduction

As a leading country in the West African sub-region and the continent, Nigeria has a robust foreign policy and security objectives that dates back to independence. As a matter of fact, Nigeria has been at the forefront of peacekeeping, security, and the overall well-being of the people at the continental level as well as the global stage. Nigeria has over the years been prominent in peace-making and law enforcement across the continent and beyond. Famously considered the giant of Africa because of her size in terms of human population, military strength and economic resource endowment. Indeed, Nigeria is rich in both human and material resources, making it the commercial nerve center of the African continent. This makes the country a major State player not only in Africa but also among the comity of nations at the world stage. However, the strengths of the country have however been weakened by a myriad of insecurity challenges bedeviling her in the past decades.

These insecurity challenges have spread to almost all the geo-political zones of the country without an exception. The level of insecurity however differs from one zone to another. Beginning with the North-East where it all started in 2009, this zone has been reduced to the headquarters of *Boko Haram* and other terrorist group such as its breakaway faction the Islamic State of West African Province (ISWAP) and others that are very active around the Sambisa forest and the Lake Chad axis. This zone has witnessed some of the ferocious battles

against the Nigerian Military with several Commanders on both sides paying the supreme price. It has also experienced territories lost to the terrorist and recaptured by the military over and over. However, the Nigerian military are still very much in control of this zone as we write. The Military neutralized over 80 terrorists as they repelled a night attack on their base in the northeast state of Borno. As recent as the 6th of March, terrorist group launched an attack on Friday abducting over 300 people including women and children in the town of Ngwoshe. This is seen as a retaliatory move following the killing of three Boko Haram commanders earlier. Thus, a proof of how dire the battle for the heart of this zone has been and still is.

As regards the North-West, it has become a safe haven of all manner of armed bandits such as kidnapers, village/market raiders, armed robbers, different types of rapists and cattle rustlers among several others. Here, villagers are given ultimatum to pay taxes to the bandit leaders before they could approach their farms for harvesting. A zone, where schools, markets. Homes and wedding venues are raided at will, brides, grooms, families, well-wishers and friends are abducted, some raped and ransom demanded. In some cases, victims are released after payment while, in most cases they are killed even after ransom are paid. The inter-breeding of these various elements had metamorphosed the zone into a very lucrative kidnapping business headquarters with some bandits with jihadist fantasies/tendencies known as Mamuda, Lakurawa and others. For instance, according to

the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (2024), the country recorded a total of 2.3 million kidnapping incidents in 2024 alone, with 63.5 per cent of the incidents occurring in the zone, with not less than 2.2 trillion naira paid in ransom in the same year.

In a similar manner, the North-Central zone has degenerated into a theatre of violent confrontations between cattle herders and crop farmers over access to and use of ecological resources such as farming lands, grazing fields and water points. This has resulted in one of the longest cyclical battles where the herders win today and the farmers win tomorrow. Many families and villages have been wiped off the surface of the earth through attacks and counter attacks for decades now with both state and Federal Government unable to find a lasting solution. Here, people are permanently displaced and cannot farm their lands hence adding to food insecurity and poverty in the country.

The South-East zone is not an exception to insecurity. It has become highly insecure as a result of the incessant agitations by a group called the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) among other ethnic militias, criminal gangs and kidnapers. However, the activities of IPOB stood out following their imposition of a “sit at home order” on Mondays as a form of civil disobedience to the state and federal government. and in solidarity to their leader on days of his court appearances. The enforcement of their order has resulted in the maiming,

killings and bloodletting that has destroyed the once thriving economic activities of the zone.

The South-West is also faced with insecurity challenges such as kidnapping for ransom, nomadic terrorism, ritual killings, cultist clashes and armed robbery among others. In fact, the failure of the Nigerian State to effectively manage the security challenge emanating from the nomadic activities of Fulani cattle herders has resulted to more security challenges in the South-West where an entire village was invaded by supposed killer Fulani’s murdering over a 170 people in one day without any consequences.

The oil rich South-South of the Niger Delta is not immune to insecurity as the zone has been characterized by agitations for resource control for decades. The discovery and production of crude oil for decades resulted in serious environmental degradation through oil spillages and gas flaring that destroyed the source of livelihood of the regions inhabitants. It eventually resulted in armed struggle with the youths adopting kidnapping of foreign oil workers for ransom and outright shutting down of oil facilities as a way of driving across their displeasure to the government. These activities resulted to a drastic reduction of crude oil and gas production. For instance, Nigeria’s oil production was reduced to about 800,000 barrels per day (bpd). The then Central Bank Governor of Nigeria (CBN) also posited that over 600,000 barrels of oil are lost due to militia activities in the Niger Delta. As oil production continued to dwindle due to their militancy, the federal government under late President Umaru

Musa Yar'Adua granted them amnesty on the condition of surrendering of all arms in their possession within a time frame for their rehabilitation. Despite these, the zone remains a hot bed of conflict with clashes between rival cult/militant groups erupting from time to time, kidnapping, with oil theft /bunkering still very much active till today.

The aforementioned internal security situations in Nigeria have adversely affected her image and status as a major contributor to peace keeping operations in the African continent and the rest of the World. Nigeria, which is reputed for assisting other smaller countries such as Chad, Niger, Sierra-Leone and Liberia among others to manage their security challenges, now relies on the support of these countries to fight the Boko Haram and other criminal elements. The various security challenges facing the country seem to be overwhelming so much so that the country is now reduced to a shadow of its former self on the continent. For instance, the series of communal conflicts, herders-farmers' conflicts, terrorists attacks and the nefarious activities of armed bandits have continued to threaten the country's national security and corporate existence (Fadeyi and Muhammed 2019). It can be correct to say that the presence of insecurity in any environment constitutes threats to lives and properties, hinders business activities and discourages local and foreign investors, as these and more goes a long way to reduce the socio-economic development of any nation.

In the same vein, the foreign policy which any country adopts is a reflection of her domestic

policy. The internal security situation is one of the components of the domestic policy as well as some aspects of the current internal security challenges especially towards determining if those have foreign policy consequences or not (Azazi, 2012, p.118). This implies that the internal security situation of a country directly or indirectly affects her foreign policy and her relationship with other countries in the international community Presently, Nigeria is currently relying on other countries to help her on the fight against insecurity which seems to be almost intractable as it has taken away the right of the citizens to have and live a secured life. For instance, Nigeria is presently partnering the United States Army to help her on intelligence sharing that will help curb insecurity and bring it under control. For instance, the US bombing of the Lakurawa position on last year Christmas eve in Sokoto State and the current ongoing collaboration which witness the arrival of about 150 US military intelligence officers who are here to train members of the Nigerian Armed Forces on counter insurgency and intelligence gathering is an indication of the situation of things on ground.

It is against this backdrop that this paper examines insecurity as it affects Nigeria's foreign policy in the last decades. The paper is divided into seven sections beginning with the introduction, section two focuses on conceptual clarifications and section three covers the theoretical framework of analysis. Section four examines the forms of insecurity, with section five looking at the causes of insecurity in the

country. Section six addresses government's responses to insecurity challenges, and in section seven the effects of insecurity on Nigeria's foreign policy is examined. Section eight concludes the paper and gives some useful policy recommendations as a panacea to the insecurity crisis in the country.

Conceptual Clarification

Insecurity - this refers to lack of security or a situation of uncertainty when a person, group or community is at the stage of been subjected to or exposed to danger at a given location (Ladan, 2019). According to Webster dictionary (2019), insecurity can also be defined as a situation in which someone is not adequately guarded, protected or defended by the authorities that are supposed to provide security. Insecurity simply connotes threats, attacks on individuals and properties or anything that undermines the safety of individuals, groups, their rights, properties in a state and that of the state (Joshua, 2014a). From all indication, Nigeria and Nigerians are suffering from high level of insecurity as successive governments down to the present have all failed to protect the country as well as the citizenry since, people can be attacked at their homes, schools, worship centers, offices, other places, at any time and are generally no longer safe in any part of the country.

Security - is a significant issue which conveys different meanings to scholars, analysts, policy makers and organisations across the globe. Fundamentally, security has to do with the presence of peace, safety, gladness and the

protection of human and physical resources or absence of crisis or threats to human dignity, all of which facilitate development and progress of any human society. According to Buzan (2016), security has to do with liberty from every form of threat and preservation of the state and its territories. For Afolabi (2023), security is about freedom from threat and the ability of states to maintain its independence and their functional integrity against forces of change, which they see as hostile while its bottom-line is survival. Security is generally agreed to be about the feeling of being safe from harm, fear, anxiety, oppression, danger, poverty, defence, protection and preservation of core values and threat to those values (Bodunde et al, 2014).

Foreign Policy

According to Holst (1995), foreign policy is seen as the actions of a state towards the external environment and the conditions usually domestic under which these actions are formulated. For Nnoli (1978), foreign policy is a nation's reactions to its external environment that involves the organization of both domestic and external relations. Adeniran (1993) further opines that the best way to describe foreign policy is to explain it as what it is. He argues that foreign policy is made up of three components. First, it is a state's overall orientation, intentions and course of action toward another, and secondly, it is the goal or objective that a state seeks to achieve in its relations or interactions with other states, and finally, it remains a means by which that goal or objective is achieved. Thus, it can be correct to conclude that Nigeria's

foreign policy from independence has been to sponsor and safeguard her national interests in her interactions with other states in the global system with special interest on the African continent first.

However, it is also imperative to state here that it is not all international contacts that can be termed foreign policy. This stems from the fact that foreign policy covers only those activities that are sponsored, supported or are known by the government. Therefore, it can be correct to assert that those actions that are international by nature but which are conducted without the knowledge of the government cannot be under the umbrella of foreign policy.

In a similar vein, most authors assume that foreign policy of states always emanates from the internal environment. This notion cannot always be true as it failed to take into cognizance the place of weak, dependent states that lacks the capability to pursue autonomous actions due to their dependent status in the international system. For these very unfortunate countries, their foreign policy actions can be said to emanate from the external environment and they are further confronted by external forces that are beyond their control.

Nigeria's Foreign Policy

Foreign policy is an essential instrument for nations to interact with other states and non-state players in the international system (Levy, 2013: 301). Nigeria's foreign policy encompasses the strategies and principles guiding its interactions with other states and international institutions. It operates through laid down

procedures that helps assess its acceptability. Since independence, Nigeria's foreign policy under various regimes have pursued almost the same objectives but through different styles but the substance has remained the same. For instance, it has undergone shifts from Pan-African solidarity and non-alignment to democratic diplomacy and economic pragmatism, etc. However, Afrocentrism remains a core principle that has been shaping engagements in peacekeeping, mediation, and regional integration.

Theoretical Clarification

This study is anchored on the Linkage Politics framework of analysis. Linkage conventionally means the act of joining together in relation to politics and international relations. The concept was propounded by Rosenau in 1967, when he coined the concept linkage politics (Dougherty and Pfaltzgraff, 1997). He sees it as a recurrent sequence of behavior that originates in one state and is reacted to in another. It explains how domestic and international politics are interconnected.

The theory is based on the following assumptions:

A, That. there is an intricate interconnection between the domestic and the external forces and this connection has the potential to determine the course of relations and how that state behaves. The theory posits that internal factor within a country, such as political stability, economic condition, and social issues, can influence its external relations and foreign policy (Saliu, 2019). In the Nigerian situation, linkage

theory can be applied to understand how domestic insecurity affects foreign policy. For instance, domestic insecurity such as insurgency and terrorist groups like Boko Haram and ISWAP have led to significant violence and instability, particularly in the north-eastern part of Nigeria.

B, That the theory recognizes the existence of two distinct environments with each having its own peculiar character. That is, the domestic environment of individual states and their external environment as against one - dimensional focus at one level of activity. The internal environment consists of the prevalent social, political and economic conditions of the nation states, the external environment is made up of attitudes and perceptions of other actors towards a particular nation-state. This manifests in international public opinion, propaganda and a host of overt or covert actions aimed at influencing the trend of actions. Similarly, rampant banditry and kidnapping in various regions have also contributed to a sense of widespread insecurity. Periodic ethnic and communal clashes among different ethnic groups and communities have further exacerbated insecurity. These persistence insecurity in Nigeria have led to a negative perception internationally that have impacted on tourism, foreign investment, and diplomatic relations. For instance, the American government had issued an advisory urging its citizens who are not on essential duties to leave Nigeria and also to avoid traveling to the north-

east and north-west zones. It even led to the closure of the American Embassy for some days. C, That the society is not a monolithic structure but is made up of complex network of structures and super structures that interact to give meaning to the whole society. Therefore, impulses from these inter-relations are what defines the nature of the domestic environment. Conversely, the international environment is subjective, given the realist character of the system. This therefore makes interactions between the two environments to be dialectical at times, which further underscores the linkage between them. By implication, the linkage theory has placed emphasis on the fact that, for one to fully comprehend why states behave the way they do in the international system, efforts must be made to understand the dynamics of the domestic as well as the external contexts within which the actions take place. For instance, there are human rights concerns about reports of human rights abuses by security forces in dealing with these security challenges that can tarnish Nigeria's image as a country that does not have value for human rights and rule of law. The insecurity in the north-east had resulted to internal displacement and migration that have affected neighbouring countries as regards refugee and migrant issues thus creating regional instability. This has led to a strain in Nigeria's relationship with its neighbours and the international communities causing diplomatic pressure in the process. Some countries and international organization have exerted diplomatic pressure on Nigeria to address the

root causes of insecurity and ensure a better governance for its citizens. In all, linkage theory helps us to understand how Nigeria's internal security issues are not just domestic concerns but also have significant implications for international standing and foreign relations.

The linkage theory is relevant to this study as it argues that for one to appreciate the behavioural pattern of nation states in the international system, due diligence should be made in understanding some pertinent factors within a nation and outside it that influence its behavior towards its external environment. However, it is also worthy of note that it is not always easy to identify these factors both in the domestic and the external environments as a number of developments can be at play at the two environments that may thwart efforts at identifying the factors and also being able to establish their link to a particular external policy

Forms of insecurity

Over the decades, Nigeria's insecurity challenges have moved from one form to another bolstering into something much bigger, deadlier and more devastating on the citizenry with greater consequences for the nation at large.

Militancy – This majorly refers to the activities of aggrieved youths in the Niger Delta region of the country over their perceived marginalization by the federal government and in their quest to seek for attention became disruptive and destructive in their actions. This eventually led to amnesty, demilitarization, demobilization and rehabilitation under late president Yar'Adua.

Terrorism – this involves the use of brute force at maiming, killing and causing general unrest among populations. Presently, the modern terrorist stands at an advantageous position thanks to new technology which has increased its destructive capability and as such is a threat to all spheres of human existence. From the activities of the Boko Haram group that has metamorphosed into ISWAP. The problem of terrorism is still very much with us leaving people in perpetual fear, and limiting individual freedom of movement as terrorist groups engage in planting improvised IEDs anywhere and anytime which they detonate killing civilians as well as security personnel majorly in the north-east and north-west zones. This have been going on for decades now and taking with it tolls of human lives and leaving behind destruction of lives by maiming as well as the massive destructions of properties both private and state owned.

Kidnapping – this is a systemic fallout of the militancy strategy adopted in the south-south zone during its hay-days but has today become a common feature of the Nigerian landscape where individuals or group of travelers are kidnapped on the highway and in some cases are taken from the comfort of their homes. They are kept in an inhumane condition mostly in the forest till ransom is paid or they're killed. In some sad instances, even after collecting millions of naira, the victims are still being killed as payment of ransom does not guarantee the release of victims in one piece. This is presently a national tragedy as schools have become the main targets of these

unwholesome acts. As it has also metamorphosed into mass kidnaping of children from school hence a major threat to education in the country.

When it comes to kidnapping, the entire country is affected as no part of the country is safe, from the villages and country sides up to the cities and state capitals. Even the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) is not an exemption, as kidnapping is now a daily business and a very sad occurrence in Nigeria. In addition, anyone today can be a victim of kidnapping, regardless of age, gender, status or wealth.

Banditry – This is a form of organized crime that has ravaged several states in the country, resulting in widespread violence, displacement, kidnapping, cattle rustlings and economic disruptions. According to Olaniyan and Yahaya (2016), the pervasive banditry and its associated threats to security have enveloped the North-west geo-political zone of Nigeria particularly Zamfara, Katsina, Sokoto, Kebbi and Kaduna states which have become a worrisome national security issues of public concerns. Similarly, the incidences of banditry are not limited to the North-west zone alone as it is also very prevalent in some parts of the North-central geopolitical zone comprising of Niger, Nasarawa, Plateau and Benue which are equally regarded as their hotbeds (Kuma and Jibrin, 2016). This has become a notorious way of life in the North-west zone of Nigeria where people are attacked, maim, killed and displaced on a daily-bases by these criminal elements known as bandits.

Separatist Agitation -This has become music to the ears of Nigerians, following the tendency of some ethnic-cultural elements to want to opt out of the corporate Nigeria with a view of asserting their own rights of self-determination. For the Igbo ethnic group, it is their conviction that their lives and properties are under constant threat and could no longer be guaranteed in the corporate Nigeria (Omemma, 2016). This resulted in the Nigerian civil war of 1967 that ended in the early 1970s where Biafra was defeated and they all remained as one Nigeria. However, a new wave of Biafra consisting of mainly the youth who still feel marginalized are still advocating for a breakaway from Nigeria. This group goes by the name the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) although already proscribed by the Federal Government. This group was able to initiate, direct and enforce a sit-at-home order to be primarily observed on Mondays as a show of civil disobedience since 2021 in other to protest the detention of its leader Nnamdi Kanu by the Federal Government and also on any other days that the IPOB leader would appear in court for trials. However, his trials had been completed and he is currently serving prison terms in Sokoto state for treason. Conversely, this directive resulted in mayhem, outright killing of anyone seen outside his home, at the markets, at schools among others, leaving behind trails of deaths and destruction of both private and government properties.

Causes of Insecurity

Several factors have been advanced by scholars, political analyst as the root causes of insecurity in Nigeria. Some of them are as follows:

Corruption – Corruption in Nigeria is not accidental, it is organized and well thought out. It is sustained by deliberate policy failures, political motivation and alliances as well as selective law enforcement strategies by those in charge looking the other way. The rate at which insecurity is spreading in this country can also be traced to wide range of corruption at all levels of government. Nigeria is not poor because money and the source change channel in an unequal way, but because it privatizes important facets of public life, bypassing representation, and choice processes (Zubairu, 2020), hence the massive corruption that is witnessed today.

Over the years, the Nigerian government has implemented various anti-corruption measures to combat the pervasive issue of corruption. These efforts include the establishment of anti-corruption agencies like the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) and the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC). Additionally, initiatives such as asset recovery, whistle-blower programme, and institutional reforms have been introduced to tackle corruption, all to no avail. Nigeria has collaborated and still is with international partners, such as United Nations, the World Bank, and the African Union, to strengthen its anti-corruption efforts. International cooperation that provides support in areas such

as capacity building, asset recovery, and sharing best practices in combating corruption. Civil society organizations and the media also play a crucial role in exposing corruption and holding public officials accountable in Nigeria. Advocacy campaigns, investigative journalism, and public awareness initiatives have helped to raise awareness about the detrimental effects of corruption and the push for greater transparency and accountability. Despite efforts to combat corruption, Nigeria continues to face challenges in effectively addressing the issue. These challenges include weak enforcement of all anti-corruption laws, political interference, impunity among corrupt individuals. Thus, corruption in Nigeria is closely linked to insecurity in the country and exacerbates existing security challenges in several ways directly or otherwise.

Religious conflicts – Nigeria has experienced period of religious conflicts that dates back over five decades and can rightly be described as a deeply divided country. According to (Dangusau, 2026) religious conflicts in Nigeria breeds insecurity and has become a tool for political manipulation, economic backwardness and social instability leading to slag in national development. These religious conflicts have been affecting Nigeria since the early 1980s and has continued to rear its ugly head up to the present day. He further posits that for the much of the Twentieth century, religious conflicts in Northern Nigeria has reached an alarming rate resulting in assassinations, serious destruction of lives and properties, impunity, lawlessness and a host of other insecurity threats that have

fractured the Christian – Muslim relationship in the country. By implication, there is cause for all to worry about the spate of religious conflicts in the country due to its disruptive and dysfunctional impact on the society (Dangusau, 2026). This decades of permanent mutual distrust between the two main religion in the country helps to fan the embers of disunity and feeds deep into the insecurity situation of today. Proliferation of arms and ammunition – The near permanent state of insecurity in Nigeria can be attributed to the proliferation of arms and ammunition. Today, guns are no longer the preserve of the military and the police force but have fallen into the hands of criminal gangs, death squads, terrorists, ethnic militias and other criminally minded individuals around the world (Peterside, 2018: 853). Furthermore, the proliferation of small arms and light weapons has remained a threat to peace and security and is also a significant promoter of armed criminality in northern Nigeria. Quite a number of unrecognized groups and non-state actors, including bandits, have easy access to arms and dangerous weapons. A recent estimate found that a high percentage of all arms and ammunition circulating in West Africa is in Nigeria (Osimen, Anegbode and Adi,2020; *Amani Africa*, 2022). Presently, some well-known terrorists or bandit leaders are seen displaying various guns and ammunition on X and TikTok for sale in Nigeria without any consequences.

In addition, other factor boosting the security challenges facing the country as regards the

proliferation of arms and ammunition in Nigeria is the porous nature of the country’s borders. This has made it very easy for criminal elements such as arms traffickers, smugglers and gun runners to have a field day by illegally importing dangerous weapons of warfare into the country due to the porosity advantage it gives them. Corroborating this position, Adejo, (2005) posits that the 2,000 miles of border that Nigeria shares with Niger, Chad, and Cameroon host almost 1,500 illegal or unmonitored crossing routes. This therefore makes it a walk over for illegal arms dealers to ply their trade with ease hence, it is not uncommon to see all manner of Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALWs) in the hands of unauthorized individuals in the country.

Conversely, Nosiri and Ohazurike (2016), does not believe that the extensive Nigerian border is the problem. Rather, they posit that the poor management of the vast and porous Nigerian borders, in terms of the ratio of entry points to the number of security border operatives, as well as the debilitating and outmoded nature of border management facilities, are the fundamental issues. Thus, Mohammed (2017), are advocating for modern gadgets that are required to guarantee proper monitoring of the boundary lines that are not on the ground. Furthermore, citing Ogba (2005) Nzeako and Abdulsalam (2021:166) disclosed that the problems posed by arms smuggling are complex and multidimensional in character as they are entangled with other broad security and societal issues such as criminal activity and links to

terrorism. It also has serious implications on human rights and humanitarian activities.

Similarly, effective transnational collaboration between Nigeria and its neighbours is lacking, particularly at the regional level. As it stands, arms circulation in the hands of non-state actors, terrorists and armed bandits cannot be tackled through local or national security frameworks alone. This reality is evident in the fact that despite the massive investment in Nigeria's security outfit, armed bandits have continued to proliferate, and protracted hostilities remain obdurate. For instance, in one season the Nigerian security forces appear to have the upper hand, and in the next season, they are on the retreat (United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), 2021).

In addition, the expected level of security partnership and military support from neighbouring countries has not permanently been forthcoming. However, the African Union (AU) and the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) have clearly condemned the uncontrolled proliferation of arms however, little or no significant progress has been made in restoring peace and order in the West African sub-region.

Poverty – the high rate of poverty is yet another major driver of insecurity and is responsible for rising level of insecurity in the country. Nigeria was once described as the poverty head quarter of the World and has been unable to free itself from that label due to some policies of the present administration that has continued to push millions of the citizenry into poverty.

According to the World Bank in Nigeria Development Update released in April (2026), titled “Nigeria’s Tomorrow Must Start Today: The Case for Early Childhood Development” Nigeria’s poverty rate rose to 63 per cent in 2025. The report showed poverty rising from 56 per cent in 2023 to 61 per cent in 2024 before reaching the present 63 per cent in 2025, an equivalent to about 140 million Nigerians living below the poverty line. Similarly, a study by Kabiru and Arshad, (2018) suggested that the prevalence of abject poverty in the rural areas of Nigeria’s North-western zone made some people to work as informants or logistic suppliers to armed bandits operating from their hide-outs in the forests. According to Zakariya’u (2019) the rate of kidnapping for ransom is alarming in the North owing majorly to high rate of poverty. The more the poverty, the more the rate of crime will increase in both rural areas and urban centers. Abdulrashid, Saifullahi and Amir (2018) revealed that rustling of cattle has deepened the vicious cycle of poverty in most rural communities in the Northern part of the country. Unemployment – is prominent among the factors that contributes to rising cases of violent crimes, thuggery, terrorism, armed banditry and therefore adds to insecurity in Nigeria. The countries’ tertiary institutions graduate thousands of students yearly who have no hope of where they would work after the 12 months mandatory National Youth Service Corp (NYSC). In the same vein, the country’s unemployment rate keeps rising annually with great implications on national security of the country.

Since there are no adequate jobs to go around, the teeming population of youth of the country who has to make a living somehow, has been made vulnerable to become cheap recruits as armed bandits, logistic suppliers for terrorists, political thugs and fraudsters among other criminal activities. The rates of unemployment may further increase as farming activities are presently threatened by armed banditry and kidnapping (Ladan, 2019). In addition, the National Bureau of Statistics in 2024 (Q2) put Nigeria's unemployment rate at 4.3%. In the face of the government's inability to create an enabling environment for industrial growth with the incessant collapse of the national Grid, bad road networks and the hijack of the few available jobs by the political class. The youth, whose population continues to grow uncontrollably are sometimes tempted to develop criminal tendencies and join criminal gangs as a means of economic survival.

Government Responses to the Challenges of Insecurity

The Nigerian state has responded to these challenges with an admixture of appeasement and the application of force in what is generally termed as the carrot and stick approach. The former has to do with the adoption of dialogue, granting of amnesty, re-integration after de-radicalisation and others. The later involves the use of military action on terrorists, bandits, kidnappers and others who are engaged in gun dwell with the military, in counter insurgency action to be killed or captured in the process. Some are tried in a law court, sentenced to serve

prison terms, or to be executed depending on their level of involvement.

Connection between Insecurity and Foreign Policy

The insecurity challenges in Nigeria have extended into a sub-regional, regional, and continental concern on the one hand and a global issue on the other. For instance, when Boko Haram terrorists strikes in the northeast, it often spread to the neighbouring countries of Chad, Niger, and Cameroun with the displaced Nigerians taking refuge in those countries. Similarly, the activities of bandits in the northwest results in a large number of Nigerian refugees residing in camps in Niger republic. Thus, insecurity is presently at the center of every discussion across the globe. World over, the issue of insecurity directly or indirectly affects the status of States domestically or externally at the international level. This is because insecurity poses a severe threat to human and material well-being.

The presence of insecurity in any society constitutes threats to human lives, properties, and by extensions, peace, and development. For instance, the United States government recently authorized its non-emergency employees and their families to vacate Nigeria due to the deteriorating security situation. The warning advised their citizens to reconsider traveling to Nigeria due to crime, terrorism, unrest, kidnapping and unavailability of health care services as recently as on the 8th of April. It went further to list out over 23 States to be avoided if they must remain in the country.

Corroborating the above views (Agogbua, Mgbatogu, and Nzewi, 2022; Ani and Onyebuka, 2016), posits that insecurity represents a fundamental threat to the life and the right of people and their dignity. It also destroys the image of the country and impact negatively on economic growth and development. No doubt, insecurity mitigates businesses, small or big, as it discourages foreign investors from investing in such countries thereby constituting an economic loss.

In addition, the connection between insecurity and foreign policy in Nigeria, showed the three concentric circles that have been identified, which are within the domestic environment. That is Nigeria's relations with her immediate neighbours in West Africa, and the continent as a whole. These circles dwell on Nigeria's relations with African neighbours, which are on peace, development, and democratization, and also the organizations, institutions, and states outside Africa (Adebayo, 2018). From the time of the founding fathers of Nigeria, successive government over the years, have ensured that these objectives are strictly adhered to. This study opines that over the past decades, insecurity has impacted negatively on Nigeria's foreign policy as foreign investors no longer see the country as profitable for business, thereby affecting the economy as an important instrument of foreign policy which rubs off on unemployment thereby resulting in some of the challenges witnessed today.

Furthermore, the claim to being the giant of Africa has been eroded following these incessant

challenges. This is due to the ceaseless attacks on the military formation by the Boko Haram terrorists, the ISWAP groups, and other bandit elements that has impacted negatively on the pride of the country's military which is an important foreign policy instrument. Also, the inability to put a stop to this crisis of insecurity for decades now have washed away the image of the country at the global level and have subjected Nigeria and her military apparatus to mockery within the continent and beyond.

Conclusion

This study insecurity and Nigeria's foreign policy has examined insecurity as a whole by looking at Nigeria dressed in the garments of kidnapping, militancy, terrorism, banditry, ethnic, cultural cum religious conflict, among others as all political with an element of criminality. It can also be correct to posit that politics has a hand in the insecurity going on in Nigeria in the past decades and that politics can determine to a large extent how insecurity is managed or curtailed. This study strongly feels that the challenges of insecurity can be resolved through the instrument of politics if and when the leadership takes decisive actions to curb the challenges. The Christmas eve bombing of the Lakurawa position in Sokoto State by the American military and the reference of Nigeria by the United States President Trump 'as a country of particular concern' cannot be unconnected with our insecurity challenges. This directly and indirectly points to the failure of leadership in Nigeria and by extension our foreign policy. For Nigeria and her foreign policy to flourish again and overcome

her enormous insecurity challenges, we need good and purposeful leadership that will attract dedicated followership to get us out of our present predicament. It has been asserted by scholars in different foras, that Nigeria has everything to make her citizens comfortable and great however, the country has always been faced with bad leadership both in the past and at present. Ironically, what we have in Nigeria today is nothing but leaders who are very greedy, corrupt, clueless, and lack vision for generation yet unborn.

Recommendations

From decades of insecurity challenges that has blossomed to a hydra-headed monster of today with no end in sight consuming everyone and everything it comes in contact with, taking tolls of lives at will, destruction of families, maiming both the military and civilians, taking over territories and the futures of innocent children and generations unborn. The study therefore recommends the following:

- Nigeria must search for a new crop of patriotic leadership that are dynamic, young, energetic and courageous to lead both the military and the nation to peace, growth and development.
- The country must adopt new measures as regards security by allocating more resources for

References

Abdulrashid, I., Saifullahi, S. I. & Amir, A. (2016). The incidences and impacts of cattle rustling in some rural communities in Katsina state, Nigeria. *FUDMA Journal of sciences*, 2 (2), 288-296.

both physical and cyber security, acquiring new technology in military hardware, intelligence gathering so as to wipe out the terrorists, bandits, kidnappers and others. In addition, the moral of the military must be boosted by real enhanced welfare packages.

- The formulators and implementors of Nigerian foreign policy machinery should have the policies re-jigged for more activities and visibilities of the positive achievements of the military forces especially as regards counter terrorism by increasing communication and diplomacy with the outside world so as to enhance the country's foreign image; engage more in international partnership and collaboration.
- Both the State and Federal Government should embark on re-branding the image of the country to counter the out flow of negative news about it through the use of modern technology to attract international interest and improve her image.
- The country should adopt public-private partnerships to create employment opportunities as this would go a long way in curbing the insecurity challenges which at the same time will lead to the return of investors and development.

Adejo,, P. Y. (2005). Crime and cross-border movements of weapons. Handbook for the training of armed and security forces, Geneva: United Nations Institute of Disarmament Research.

- Adeniran, T. (1993). Introduction to international relations. Lagos: Macmillan publishers.
- Afolabi, M. B. (2023). Concept of Security. www.researchgate.net/publication/303899299.concept-of-security.
- Amani Africa (2022, May 18). Briefing on disarmament and control of illicit small arms and light weapons in Africa. Retrieved from <https://amaniafrica-et.org/briefing-on-disarmament-and-control-of-illicit-small-arms-and-light-weapons-in-africa/>
- Bodunde, D.O., Ola, A. A. & Afolabi, M. B. (2014). Internal Security in Nigeria. The irony of multiplicity of security outfits and security challenges in IMPACT: IJRHAC, 2(5)
- Agbu, O. (2021). Nigeria's Foreign Policy: A Historical and Contemporary Analysis. *Nigerian Journal of International Affairs*, 47(2), 101–123.
- Azazi, O.A (2012) Internal Security and Nigerian Foreign Policy in Anyaoku E (ed) Review of Nigeria's Foreign Policy: Issues and Perspectives. Lagos: NIIA.
- Dangusau, M. S. (2026). Religious conflicts Nigeria since the Twentieth century: causes, implications and the path Forward. Ed in Leadership, Governance, Security and Developments in Africa: A Festschrift in honour of Prof. M. S. Audu. Lokoja: Federal University Lokoja printing press.
- Dougherty, J. E. & Pfaltzgraff, R.L. (1996). Contending theories of international relations. New York: Longman publishers.
- Fadeyi, J.T. & Muhammad A. (2019) Communal Conflict and National Security in Nigeria: Selected case studies. Retrieved from <https://papers.ssrn.com/Delivery.cfm>
- Holsti, K. J. (1995). International politics: A framework for analysis (7th ed.) New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Joshua, S. (2014a). Politics and power in inter-group conflicts: Evidence from Jos, Nigeria. *Convenant university Journal of Politics and International Affairs* 3 (1), 22-37.
- Ladan, S. I. (2019). Analysis of contemporary insecurity in Katsina State, Nigeria. *Direct Research Journal of Social Sciences and Educational Studies* 6 (7) 95-102.
- Mohammed, H. S. (2017). Nigeria's border and its effect on the economic and security development: A case of northern borders in Nigeria. *American Finance & Banking Review*, 61.
- Nnoli, O. (1978). Self-reliance and foreign policy in Tanzania. New York: No publishers.

- Nosiri, U. D., & Ohazurike, E. U. (2016). Border security and national security in Nigeria. *South East Journal of Political Science*. 2 (2), 214-225.
- Nzeako, U. S. & Abdulsalam, M. R. (2021). The smuggling and Proliferation of small arms and light weapons (SALWs) within the West African sub-region: A contemporary appraisal. *UZU Journal*. 8 (1), 165-195.
- Olaniyan, A. & Yahaya, A. (2016). Cows, bandits, and violent conflicts: understanding cattle rustling in northern Nigeria. *Africa Spectrum*, 5 (3), 93-105.
- Omemma, D. A. (2016). The Nigerian state and the challenges of managing centrifugal forces. *Studies in Politics and Society* 4, (1), 288-301.
- Osimen, G. U., Anegbode, E. J., & Adi, I. (2020). The role of ECOWAS in the fight against the proliferation of small arms and light weapons in West African sub-region. *International Journal of Political Science (IJPS)*. 6, (4), 1-11.
- Peterside, Z. B. (2018). The impacts of proliferation of small arms and light weapons on the quest for national security in Nigeria. *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3 (7), 852-860.
- Saliu, H. A. (2019). Approaches to the study of international relations (ed.) Ibadan: College Press.
- The National Bureau of Statistics. Abuja, Nigeria
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (2021). Conflict analysis in the Lake Chad basin 20202021. Trends, developments and implications for peace and stability. Retrieved from https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zsek_e326/files/2022-08/Conflict%20Analysis%20in%20the%20Lake%20Chad%20Basin.pdf
- Webster, M. (2019). Definition of insecurity by Merriam Webster. Retrieved from
- Zubairu, N. (2020). Rising Insecurity in Nigeria: Causes and Solutions. *Journal of Studies in Social Science*. Infinity Press.